

Abstract on a Review of Deep Learning Methods for MRI Reconstruction

Summary and Comparison of current Approaches for Deep Learning based Magnetic Resonance Imaging Reconstruction

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INTRODUCTION

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is the most extensively used imaging method in medicine for obtaining high-quality, images of the anatomy and physiology of the human body. It provides detailed images, for non-invasive diagnosis and investigation of various diseases without harmful radiation [1]. Additionally, the potential of artificial intelligence is increasingly being applied to healthcare for medical imaging, medical data analysis and medical diagnostics. In this context, there have been numerous publications on deep learning-based MRI reconstruction applications in the last few years [2].

BACKGROUND

To capture the anatomy of a patient, MRI data is collected sequentially in time in the frequency domain referred to as k-space. To achieve higher spatial resolution and thus image quality, more k-space points must be sampled. Accordingly, longer scan times are required for better image quality. In the last 15 years, acceleration of MRI has been the subject of many studies, leading to advances such as parallel imaging and compressed sensing [1].

Meanwhile, there are several DL methods that have proven to perform better or just as good as the non-DL methods. However, the numerous approaches were developed with different data sets and are therefore difficult to compare. The work [3] has addressed this issue by providing a qualitative and quantitative comparison of eleven non-DL and DL methods.

METHODS

To this purpose, the authors provide an overview of classical k-space-based image reconstruction methods as well as state-of-the-art developments in DL methods. They explain basic DL tools and provide insight into generative and non-generative modeling procedures for MR image reconstruction. Subsequently, eleven representative methods for which the code is available online, were applied to the fastMRI knee dataset then qualitative and quantitative results were derived. The dataset consists of raw k-space data, 1594 scans acquired

on four different MRI machines. For the quantitative analysis, the metrics Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE), Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Loss function (SSIM) are calculated over the test data with 1000 samples at 4-fold and 8-fold acceleration factor. For the analysis original training, test and validation splits have been used, but only 7% of training split data, due to a width limit of 372. In addition, the authors discuss the main aspects of performance and limitations for these methods. [3].

RESULTS

The authors distinguish between non-dl (classical methods) and dl methods further subdivided into generative and non-generative methods [3].

Figure 1: MRI Reconstruction Methods [3].

The classical models contain two approaches for parallel imaging, GRAPPA-like and SENSE-like methods. The GRAPPA method regresses k-space lines from a learned kernel without being limited by specific image reconstruction constraints such as sparsity, bounded support, or smooth phase. SENSE is an image deconvolution method that extracts the periodic repetitions from the knowledge of the coil, each pixel position is a weighted sum of coil sensitivities [3].

For assessment also zero filled image reconstruction, which sets un-sampled k-space locations as zero and performs conventional inverse fourier transform, was applied [4].

As a result of the comparison, the DL methods GrappaNET, J-MoDL and VariationNET surpassed the baseline (non-DL) methods by far [3]. Classification of the methods by the authors is shown in figure 2.

Acceleration	Model	NMSE	PSNR	SSIM
8-fold	Zero Filled	0.0352	29.60	0.642
	SENSE (Pruessmann et al., 1999)	0.0261	31.65	0.762
	GRAPPA(Griswold et al., 2002)	0.0202	25.31	0.782
	RefineGAN(Quan et al., 2018)	0.0221	32.09	0.792
	DeepADMM(Sun et al., 2016)	0.0201	36.37	0.810
	LORAKI (Kim et al., 2019)	0.0181	36.45	0.882
	VariationNET (Sriram et al., 2020a)	0.0211	36.63	0.788
	GrappaNet (Sriram et al., 2020b)	0.0071	36.76	0.922
	J-MoDL (Aggarwal and Jacob, 2020)	0.0065	35.08	0.928
	Deep Decoder (Heckel and Hand, 2018)	0.0079	29.654	0.929
DIP (Ulyanov et al., 2018)	0.0076	29.18	0.912	

Figure 2: Quantitative metrics (NMSE, PSNR, SSIM) over the test data with 8-fold acceleration factor [3].

GRAPPANet achieved an improvement of ~65% for NMSE, boost of ~11.5dB for PSNR compared to GRAPPA, which was the best performing baseline method, and an excellent SSIM loss of 0.922. GRAPPANet is an end-to-end CNN Model with two subnetworks. The first fills in the missing k-space lines with a nonlinear CNN-based interpolation function (similar to GRAPPA), the second maps the filled k-space measurement to image space. VariationNET boosted PSNR by ~11.4dB with similar values for SSIM and NMSE compared to GRAPPA. VariationNET is a type of a temporal network which applies a CRNN as a proximal operator to reconstruct by inverse mapping from k-space. J-MoDL achieved an improvement of ~68% for NMSE, boost of ~9.8dB for PSNR and remarkable SSIM of 0.928. The active acquisition-based method J-MoDL optimizes sampling reconstruction by utilizing jointly a data consistency and a regularization network [3].

Figure 3: Qualitative comparison of 8x acceleration results on fast MRI knee dataset [3].

The Deep Decoder and DIP methods also accomplished a decent performance using untrained networks, which is valuable since this generalizes to different MR reconstruction settings. Untrained network model Deep Decoder employs pixel-wise linear combinations of channels and joint weights in spatial dimensions that together help to learn relationships and features of nearby pixels. Deep Image Prior method DIP uses a randomly weighted autoencoder, that reconstructs a clean image given a fixed noise vector [3]. The qualitative results (Fig. 3) show over-smoothing for the zero filled and SENSE reconstructed images with a lack of high-frequency features. In contrast, these clinically relevant details become readily apparent with GRAPPANet, VariationNET and J-MoDL [3].

CONCLUSION

The results show that deep learning-based methods offer a high potential for MRI reconstruction due to very good quantitative and qualitative results but also have to deal with the negative characteristics of DL methods. However, recent publications using new DL methods indicate great improvements in terms of reconstruction of minute details/anatomical structures, risk quantification, running time complexity and generalization. The authors conclude by pointing out that more than one data set should be used for a comprehensive comparison and that only a fraction of the methods could be tested due to the high number of implementations. Finally, standardized datasets with different degrees of complexity, noise level and ground truth availability are required to ensure comparability between the numerous newly developed methods [3].

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